

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.1410003

УДК 351.82

*Husarov K., Senior researcher of Educational, Scientific and Production center,
National University of Civil Protection of Ukraine, Kharkiv*

PREVENTION OF STATUS INCOMPATIBILITY IN FORCED RELOCATIONS: THE PUBLIC-MANAGEMENT ASPECT

The article deals with the relationship between the emergence of status incompatibility and internal migration processes. The peculiarities of the process of status incompatibility in Ukraine after the annexation of the Crimean peninsula and military operations on the territory of the Lugansk and Donetsk regions are investigated. Proposed measures to reduce the level of status incompatibility among internally displaced persons.

Keywords : *internal migration, state administration, status incompatibility.*

У статті розглянуто взаємозв'язок між виникненням статусної несумісності і внутрішніми міграційними процесами. Досліджено особливості процесу статусної несумісності в Україні після анексії Кримського півострова та військових дій на території Луганської та Донецької областей. Запропоновані заходи щодо зменшення рівня статусної несумісності серед вимушено переміщених осіб.

Ключові слова : *внутрішня міграція, державне управління, статусна несумісність.*

Problem setting. Migration, affecting many aspects of the life of the population, plays an important role in the socio-economic development of each country. A successful economic policy is impossible without a comprehensive consideration of such a phenomenon as population migration. Migration of the population is one of the natural phenomena that occurs in society, regardless of the form of the social and economic system and is considered in the framework and at the junctures of different sciences. The movement of the population between regions within the country and beyond, the competition between buyers of labor, employers. Such movements make it possible to create the necessary balance in the labor market and thereby stimulate the market of goods and services by increasing the demand for them, as a result of increasing incomes of the population. Internal migration is one of the prerequisites for raising the level and quality of life of the population, provided that proper state policy is maintained [1].

Nevertheless, in modern Ukrainian realities, we have to speak more about forced migration processes, which often not only do not bring economic and social

development, but, on the contrary, lead to a deterioration in the economic condition of both the individual and the state as a whole, as well as to the emergence of such a phenomenon as status incompatibility.

Recent research and publication analysis. Theoretical, methodological and applied aspects of the study of internal migration populations have been studied by foreign and Ukrainian researchers. Among Ukrainian scientists, it is especially worth mentioning the scientific works of such figures as : O. Malinovskaya, O. Poznyak, O. Kupets, O. Ostapa, L. Eliseeva, etc.

Among foreign scientific researchers, the issues of population movement outside the borders of the state have been studied by J. Devind, J. Holdaway, W. Petersen and others. However, the issues of the relationship between internal migration processes (in particular forced ones) and status incompatibilities require additional scientific research.

Paper objective. Proceeding from the foregoing, the main goal of our study is to establish a link between status incompatibility and forced migrations, which have acquired extreme urgency in the conditions of modern Ukraine, and the development of a proposal for mitigating the consequences of this phenomenon.

Paper main body. Migration processes taking place in the modern world are inexpedient and can not be compared with those that took place in the past. Activity among migrants is inversely proportional to the overall standard of living in that locality, is being considered. That is, the higher, for example, the level of employment and income, the lower the migration rate. In recent years, migration activity has increased significantly and several times higher than the figures of 20 to 30 years ago. In addition to the level of employment and income, this is due to a multitude of factors of:

- political,
- military,
- economic,
- ecological,
- ethnic nature and other factors.

In addition, the level of development of communications and the removal of restrictions on free movement, as well as awareness of the population about possible future sites of migration, contribute to the activation of migration processes [2]. It should also be mentioned that if we are talking about internal migration processes in Ukraine, recently forced migrations due to the annexation of the Crimean peninsula by the Russian Federation and military actions unleashed on the territory of Donetsk and Lugansk regions of Ukraine are implied.

The essence of such concepts as "population migration" and "mobility of the population" raises controversy among scientists. The demographic aspect of the mobility of the population means the spatial, physical or geographical displacement of the population, differs from the social aspect of mobility, in which the status of an individual changes (for example, a change in occupation). Migration and mobility are of a different nature. At the same time, these changes can concern both raising the

status of an individual and reducing it. The movement of the population with the crossing of state borders and the boundaries of administrative-territorial entities actually occurs everywhere. The movement of the population within administrative-territorial entities is much more difficult to classify. If an individual moves from one city to another within the same area, or from one area to another within the same city, then it is necessary to clearly distinguish between the concepts of "migration" and "mobility". In general, it can be said that any migration is mobility, but not all mobility is migration, since mobility does not fulfill one of the conditions in the above definitions of migration, namely: there is no change in residence for a certain period of time.

The statement that migration always promotes social development and increases the social status of individuals is not always correct. In sociology there is the concept of "status incompatibility." Every individual who lives in a society has several statuses, as he participates in numerous groups and organizations:

- labor;
- sports;
- religious;
- political, and the like.

Status incompatibility are statuses that contradict each other, destroy the harmony of the status portrait of a person [3]. In other words, a status incompatibility means a state in which the same person in different group hierarchies occupies different ranks (high, medium, low), unlike status compatibility, where the same person occupies all the same ranks (all high, all medium, all low). In a transition period in Ukraine, which is far from the ideals of Western societies, the issue of the status of incompatibility is very relevant.

The change in the political and economic system, the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula and military actions in the territory of Donetsk and Lugansk regions, the development of the informal labor market and the growth of the level of the shadow economy, have led to a decline in the social status of migrating individuals. Professional reorientation occurred in favor of professions of relevance and those that do not require significant skills, education, etc. For example, today among migrants one can meet those who have a higher education and have a higher status in society, work in construction in a low social status - as laborers (for highly educated - this is the status of incompatibility in the descending order), as the incomes they receive are several times higher than their incomes if they continued to engage in their status-prestigious activities quality. Now young people are asking themselves: is it worth continuing education in higher education institutions, if this does not contribute to the status growth and not to ensure the status of compatibility. This state of affairs is a signal for modern society and politics. If the society is not able to pay the professor according to his contribution to the science and education of people, then the society, and not the professor, is to blame for this. It is no accident in sociology that status incompatibility is understood as a social tension in the status system of societies. Thus, the status incompatibility turns into a factor of social mobility - vertical and horizon-

tal, ascending and descending. As the example of Ukrainian highly educated migrants working on non-prestigious jobs has shown, among them social mobility occurs horizontally, rather than vertically, as is customary in the countries of the European Union and North America.

In our opinion, given the fact that migration is development, this process should be used to develop backward regions and to endorse those areas of migration that would meet the interests of the uniform development of all regions of Ukraine. The main thing here is not to allow overpopulation of some territories and the extinction of others. It is necessary to understand the fact that spontaneous "village-city" migration, as well as migration from temporarily occupied territories, leads to extreme pressure on the labor market and the infrastructure of cities [4]. Proceeding from this, it is necessary to consider the equal distribution of the population and the equal development of all regions of the country, without violating the citizens right to free movement.

In developing countries, there are more internal migrants than external ones. Internal migration is mainly associated with urbanization or with the force displacement of the population, due to conflicts and natural disasters. In Ukraine, however, we are seeing a reverse situation, recently the population has been seriously reduced. The factors leading to the excess of the number of external migrations over internal ones should be:

- first of all, this is a general decline in the national economics and industry;
- inability to absorb large flows of highly educated migrants from temporarily occupied territories by the cities of the country;
- the earnings of external labor migrants exceed the earnings of internal migrants;
- the existence of a visa-free regime in the countries receiving external labor.

Accordingly, proceeding from the above, it can be concluded that the status inconsistency leads to the exit of the most qualified and highly educated population from the country.

In the development of mechanisms for public administration in the field of internal migration within the framework of a single program of the country's migration policy, in our view, special attention should be paid to the following aspects:

- effective placement of the population, from the economic point of view, is not possible without the direct participation of the state in the ongoing migration processes. However, this participation should be expressed in regulating these processes in accordance with the interests of migrants and taking into account the economic, social stability and political security of the country;
- the authorities disregard for internal displacement can lead to irreversible consequences. The government of the country needs to take urgent measures so that internal displacements become effective levers of the country's development, since the participants of internal migration processes are especially vulnerable segments of the population;
- it is necessary to draw up programs for the economic development of each

region, taking into account the growth rates of the population and the corresponding location of production capacities, which can significantly reduce undesirable flows of internal migration and reduce the volume of external labor migration;

The main deterrent factors of migration, even in conditions of temporary occupation of certain regions of Ukraine are: the availability of other sources of income and livelihoods; reluctance to leave ancestral places; the lack of migration opportunities due to the limited financial capacity of households, etc. To avoid negative flows, the relevant departments need to take timely measures:

– it is necessary to restore the country's production capacity, which will: increase the number of officially employed in the country's economy and, consequently, reduce the level of informal employment, external and internal labor migration; will provide social protection of the population; reduce the level of the shadow economy (will lead to an increase in tax revenues in the country's budget), etc.;

– should provide decent wages to workers in the formal sector of the economy, which will stop the leakage of personnel.

Conclusions. The issues of internal migration of the population and their regulation, taking into account the right of every individual to free choice of residence, improvement of the labor potential of the society and reduction of poverty level are relevant in all countries. This is especially true for Ukraine, because it is a military operations are taking place on its territory. In addition to military operations, in the period after the acquisition of state independence, the main factors of "pushing out" were economic, social, demographic, political and environmental factors. Effective population distribution is, first of all, ensuring active development of the country through the equal distribution of labor resources, the allocation of production assets mainly in less developed regions and the stimulation of the development of services in large urban centers. It is achieved only if the policy of regional development, the development of new territories and indirect stimulation of the influx of people from densely populated areas to new development areas is conducted.

References:

1. Black, R., Sward, J. "Migration, Poverty Reduction Strategies and Human Development." *Development Research Centre on Migration, Globalisation and Poverty*. 2009. Web. <https://mpr.ub.uni-muenchen.de/19222/1/MPRA_paper_19222.pdf>.

2. Castles, S. "Environmental change and forced migration: making sense of the debate." *New Issues in Refugee Research Working Paper No.70*. Geneva - United Nations High Commission for Refugees. 2002. Print.

3. Ginsburg, Carren, et al. "Healthy or unhealthy migrants? Identifying internal migration effects on mortality in Africa using health and demographic surveillance systems of the INDEPTH network." *Social Science & Medicine* 164. 2016. Print.

4. Greenwood, Michael J., 1993. "Internal migration in developed countries," *Handbook of Population and Family Economics*, in: M. R. Rosenzweig & Stark, O. (ed.), *Handbook of Population and Family Economics*, edition 1, volume 1, chapter 12, pages 647-720 Elsevier.